

Studies on Adsorption of Methyl Violet on Alumina, Silica and Zinc Oxide

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The adsorption of methyl violet from aqueous and alcoholic solutions over alumina, silica and zinc oxide have been carried out to understand the extent and mode of adsorption. The adsorption of methyl violet over these oxides exhibited either a typical H-type or L-type adsorption isotherm. The H-type adsorption is explained on the basis of 'flatwise' adsorption with some micellisation, whereas the L-type adsorption is interpreted in terms of multilayer adsorption. The Freundlich and the Langmuir equations are applicable within the limited range of dye concentration.

ONLY a few studies have been carried out on the adsorption of dyes over inorganic solids. The adsorption characteristics of a range of cationic dyes have been studied over alkaline chromatographic alumina powder¹. The nature of adsorption was interpreted from the shape of the adsorption isotherm, the ease of desorption and the effect of temperature. In most cases, adsorption occurred by ion-exchange of ionic micelles dyes. The mechanism of various azo dyes on chromatographic alumina has been studied using spectrophotometric technique². Sulphonated azo dyes were readily adsorbed by acid-treated alumina. Mono- and di-sulphonated dyes appeared to adsorb as anionic micelles, while, trisulphonated ions were proposed to be oriented flatwise as monodisperse layer. The adsorption was very fast and there was no evidence of absorption in internal pores of the solid. The adsorption studies over various hydrous ferric oxide samples were carried out by the dye crystal violet³. The adsorption properties were changed when excess or deficient amount of alkali was used in precipitating the adsorbent. The adsorption increased with increase in concentration of dye and also with rise in temperature. The Freundlich equation was not applicable over complete range of concentration.

Experimental

Chemically pure grade solid methyl violet (E. Merck) was used without further purification. Ethyl alcohol was distilled and used in alcoholic preparations. The glassware was washed with double-distilled water and the same was used in all aqueous preparations. The stock solution (100 ppm) of the dye was prepared which was covered with a double layer of black cloth to protect it from the effect of light. The test solutions were prepared by diluting the stock solution to the appropriate concentration (0.5–5.0 ppm). Chemically pure grade

solids, alumina, silica and zinc oxide (E. Merck) were used. The absorbance of dye solutions was measured by a Jasco UV-DEC 505 uv/vis spectrophotometer.

Three series of adsorption experiments were performed over the solids. In one series of experiments, alumina, silica and zinc oxide were used as 'fresh' samples, that is, the solids were not subjected to any pretreatment or purification. In another set of experiments, the adsorbents were washed with several changes of distilled water, followed by heating at 450° in a muffle furnace for about 6 h and subsequently cooling gradually to room temperature (sample called 'water washed'). In third series of adsorption studies, the solids were merely activated by heating at 450° for 6 h, followed by gradual cooling to room temperature. These samples were called 'activated' solids. All these solids were placed in the desiccator (CaCl₂) to avoid the contact of moisture. The adsorption procedure was to take weighed quantity of the adsorbent (typically 0.5 g) in a series of conical flasks, then to each flask added 25 ml of the dye test solutions with varying initial concentration (C_0). The flasks were then tumbled for 0.5 h and then kept stationary under thermostating ($25.0 \pm 1.0^\circ$) condition. The amount of the dye adsorbed (x) was calculated from the difference in the initial and the equilibrium concentration (C_e) of the solution measured spectrophotometrically. The amount of dye adsorbed per gram of the adsorbent (x/m) when plotted against C_e gave the type of adsorption isotherm. The Freundlich equation was tested by plotting the graph between $\log x/m$ against $\log C_e$ and the Langmuir equation was tested by plotting the graph between $C_e/(x/m)$ against C_e .

Several methods have been proposed for estimating the surface areas of solids, for example^{4,5}, the adsorption of nitrogen or rare gases, solute from

solutions, the examination of solids by electron microscopy X-ray diffraction, radioactive tracers, surface silvering, photo-extinction and air permeability method for estimating surface area. Amongst these techniques, the adsorption methods are frequently used. The BET equation is applied in calculating surface areas. But the apparatus employed is complex and adsorption procedure is laborious. The solute adsorption method is, however, much simple and the calculations are straightforward. Dyes are normally used because of the ease with which the coloured solutions are analysed spectrophotometrically. The surface areas of finally devided solids have been determined using methylene blue solutions by Kipling and Wilson⁶. We followed the same experimental procedure. A certain quantity (0.2 g) of solid sample was taken in a series of conical flasks and treated with alcoholic solution (25 ml) of methylene blue with graded concentrations. The flasks were sealed and tumbled for 0.5 h and then kept in thermostating conditions (25°) for a period of 24 h. The adsorption isotherm was a typical S-type isotherm⁷ which is a representative end-on adsorption of methylene blue molecule on the surface. A typical adsorption isotherm is shown in Fig. 1. The monolayer capacity (X_m) was calculated from the plateau of the iso-

Fig. 1. A typical S-type adsorption isotherm for methylene blue on silica (water-washed).

therm. The surface area was calculated from the expression⁶, Surface area = $X_m N A$; where X_m , N , A , are respectively the monolayer capacity, the Avogadro number and the area of the surface occupied by methylene blue molecule. The end-on adsorbed methylene blue molecule occupies an area of 39.5 sq. Å⁶.

Calibrations: To carry out the procedure lined above, it was necessary to draw the calibration curves for the dye solutions. The λ_{max} (590 nm) for methyl violet in aqueous and alcoholic solutions was found to be the same. The plots of the variation of absorbance against the concentration of the dye solution obeyed the Beer-Lambert law (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Calibration curves for the variation in absorbance with changing concentration of methyl violet in (A) water and (B) alcohol.

Results and Discussion

Giles *et al.*⁷ explained various types of adsorption isotherms involving different adsorption mechanisms. Amongst these isotherms, three are the most commonly applied, represented as the S-type (initially convex to the solution concentration axis and then a plateau), the L-type isotherm (initially concave to the solution concentration axis and then a plateau followed by another rise and then another plateau). The initial rise in adsorption of solute depends upon the availability of the active sites. The plateau or the inflexion point gives the indication that the surface has been saturated.

In the present studies, the adsorption behaviour was either H-type or L-type (Table 1). The H-type

TABLE 1—ADSORPTION BEHAVIOUR OF METHYL VIOLET OVER SILICA, ALUMINA AND ZINC OXIDE

Adsorbent	Adsorption behaviour	
	Solvent = Water	Solvent = Alcohol
Silica-fresh	L-type	L-type
Silica-water washed	L-type	H-type
Silica-activated	L-type	H-type
Alumina-fresh	L-type	—
Alumina-water washed	H-type	—
Alumina-activated	L-type	—
Zinc oxide-fresh ₁	H-type	—
Zinc oxide-water washed	L-type	—
Zinc oxide-activated	H-type	—

curve (Fig. 3) is a representative monolayer adsorption isotherm, where large ionic micelles of dye are formed on the surface. This behaviour has

Fig. 3. Typical adsorption isotherms of methyl violet in water (except where indicated otherwise) on various solids at $25 \pm 1.0^\circ$ on (A) activated silica (solvent = alcohol), (B) washed alumina, (C) fresh zinc oxide and (D) washed silica (solvent = alcohol).

Fig. 4. Typical L-type adsorption isotherms of methyl violet in water (except where indicated otherwise) on various solids at $25.0 \pm 1.0^\circ$ on (A) fresh alumina, (B) activate alumina, (C) activated zinc oxide, (D) washed zinc oxide and (E) fresh silica (solvent = alcohol).

been observed in the adsorption of azo dyes from water on chromatographic alumina⁸. However,

our studies show that the initial portion of the curves do not lie very near to the vertical axis (Fig. 3), therefore, a low solute affinity towards adsorbents is expected. This idea is supported by observing the low adsorption rates, as several hours were required for complete saturation of the surfaces. This may be due to the absorption in the internal amorphous regions of the solids. The rate determining step is therefore, the diffusion of dye along the walls of the pores, which might have the absorptive surface and hence exercise a 'drag' on the passage of dye molecules.

The L-type curves were also obtained in a few adsorption experiments. The L-type adsorption is a representative 'flatwise' adsorption which leads to the build-up of further layers on top of the first (Fig. 4). Similar behaviour has been observed in the adsorption of merocyanine dye over silver halides⁷. In L-type, monodisperse adsorption occurs and small size ionic micelles of dye are formed on the surface¹.

The extent of dye adsorption per gram of the solid at a fixed initial concentration of dye is presented in Table 2. It can be seen that the extent

TABLE 2—THE EXTENT OF ADSORPTION AND SURFACE AREA MEASUREMENTS

Initial concentration of methyl violet = 5.0 mg dm^{-3} ,
Solvent = water, Equilibrium time = 24 h, Weight of solid = 0.5 g

Adsorbent	Extent of adsorption (x/m) $\text{mg dm}^{-3} \text{ g}^{-1}$	Surface area $\text{m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$
Silica-fresh	8.36	13.31
Silica-water washed	8.00	2.60
Silica-activated	8.60	1.90
Alumina-fresh	2.60	19.00
Alumina-water washed	3.00	2.23
Alumina-activated	3.60	6.65
Zinc oxide-fresh	2.10	23.78
Zinc oxide-water washed	1.50	5.84
Zinc oxide-activated	2.60	6.65

of adsorption is in the order, silica > alumina > zinc oxide. This may be explained on the basis of their surface characteristics. The surface of silica is acidic in nature, whereas methyl violet is a basic dye and therefore, has greater affinity for adsorption on silica. On the other hand, alumina, being amphoteric, has comparatively less tendency for adsorption of methyl violet. Whilst, zinc oxide surface has basic properties, therefore, the lowest amount of methyl violet is adsorbed on this solid.

The surface areas of various samples were estimated using methylene blue adsorption method. The results are presented in Table 2. From the results, it can be seen that surface areas of the original samples are higher as compared to those of the 'treated' samples. There is no direct relationship between the extent of adsorption and the surface area. Surface area is by no means the only physical property which determines the extent of

adsorption. Particularly for non-metallic solids, the pore structure is also a significant factor, which contributes the total surface area. Due to heterogeneity of the surfaces, the adsorption is not always directly proportional to the surface area. The results shown in Table 2, reveal that though various pretreatments have modified the total surface area, there is no generation or loss of active centres on the surfaces under investigation.

Fig. 5. The Langmuir plot $C_e/(x/m)$ against C_e and the Freundlich plot $\log x/m$ against $\log C_e$ from aqueous methyl violet solutions on fresh zinc oxide.

The Freundlich and the Langmuir equations were tested. In a few cases, these equations were applicable within the limited range of concentrations (Fig. 5). However, in most cases, these equations were not applicable, as the mechanism whereby the dye is adsorbed is complex. This complexity may be attributed due to micellisation, aggregation and absorption of dye molecules into the bulk of solids.

References

1. C. H. GILES, I. A. EASTON and MCKAY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 4495.
2. T. CUMMINGS, H. C. GARVEN, C. H. GILES, S. M. K. REHMAN, J. G. SNEDDEN and C. E. STEWART, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 535.
3. R. B. HAJELA and S. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 781.
4. S. J. GREGG, "The Surface Chemistry of Solids", 2nd ed., Chapman & Hall, London, 1961.
5. H. E. ROSS, "The Measurement of Particle Size in Very Fine Powders", Constable & Co., London, 1953.
6. J. J. KIPLING and R. B. WILSON, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1960, 10, 109.
7. C. H. GILES, T. H. MACEWAN, S. N. NAKHWA and D. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3973.
8. C. H. GILES and S. N. NAKHWA, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1962, 12, 266.